

Completeness of Cyclic Entailment Proofs in Separation Logic with Inductive Predicates and Arithmetic (Technical Report)

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Abstract. An effective and efficient entailment proof system is essential to a verification system using separation logic. In this work, we consider a decision procedure that could deduce linear validity proofs (i.e., without back-tracking) for the quantifier-free entailment problem. Particularly, we present a sound, complete and terminating cyclic proof system for the problem in separation logic combining with linearly inductive predicates and arithmetic properties. We have implemented the proposal in a prototype tool and evaluated it over challenging problems taken from a recent separation logic competition. The experimental results show the effectiveness and efficiency of the proposed system.

1 Introduction

In the last two decades, separation logic [20,35] has been very successful in automatically reasoning about programs that manipulate pointer structures. The primary advantage of separation logic is the support of compositional reasoning which leads to reusability and scalability [7,8]. Particularly, proofs of the compositional verification are typically reduced into entailment problems. That is, given an antecedent A and a consequent C (where A and C are formulas in separation logic), the entailment problem is the act of checking whether $A \models C$ holds. Therefore, an efficient decision procedure for these entailments is the vital ingredient of an automatic verification system in separation logic. To succinctly and precisely specify functional specifications of programs, separation logic is typically combined with predicate definitions and pure properties (e.g., sortedness, parent pointers) [10,26,31,33]. In this context, one key challenge of a decision procedure is the capability to support for entailments that often require inductive reasoning about unbounded heaps and their data contents. The problem of induction is very difficult, especially for an automated inductive theorem proving where induction rules are not explicitly stated. Indeed, this problem (even without arithmetic) was shown to be undecidable [1]. Hence, one research goal is to develop a sound and complete entailment procedure in a decidable yet expressive separation logic fragment.

Perhaps, the mainstream solution to the inductive entailments is the cyclic proof systems introduced by Brotherston [4,5,6] and two variants: structural inductive inference in Constraint Logic Programming [11] and mutual inductive inference in separation logic with arithmetic constraints [38]. The essence of the cyclic proof is that induction rules are replaced by the generation of cycles with back-links using some weakening and substitution principles. Recently, completeness of the cyclic proof system has been

shown in [40]. However, this completeness only stays within a fragment with non-empty and heap-only inductive definitions and without arithmetic properties.

In this work, we bridge the gap by introducing the first sound, complete and terminating cyclic entailment proof system for a combination of shape and arithmetic properties. The decidable fragment, called SHLIDe, is an extension of separation logic with recursive definitions of linear predicates and *local* properties. The predicates in our system could represent (possibly nested and mutual) list segments, skip lists and trees. Local properties of a predicate (such as a list with fast-forward pointers and all nodes contain the same integer number, a nested list being sorted, a tree being a binary search tree [22,27]) are those invariants which are universally quantified over the predicate and their validity can be verified locally through small models of finite heap domains.

Similar to Brotherston’s cyclic proof system [5,40], our induction principle is based on the least semantics of recursive definitions. That is the soundness of cyclic proofs are based on *infinite* one-step *unfolding* (which is similar to well-ordering traverse) of recursive data structures. In contrast, our system contains two main differences. First, for completeness the proof search is designed such that frame rule (i.e., $A \models C \Rightarrow A * F \models C * F$ where $*$ is the separating conjunction) is applied restrictively to avoid unexpected weakening. Secondly, while the soundness of the generated back-links in [5,40] must be checked globally and explicitly, every back-links generated in SHLIDe is sound locally. Moreover, unfolding inductive predicates in consequent of an entailment typically generates disjunctive formulas. To enhance completeness, proof search over these disjuncts together with back-tracking needs to be applied. This would reduce the efficiency of a system. To overcome, we present a normal form that helps to avoid the proof search and back-tracking. Hence, our system is potentially more efficient.

Contributions Our primary contributions are summarized as follows.

- We present a decidable fragment and a novel decision procedure for the entailment problem in separation logic with linearly inductive definitions and arithmetic.
- We provide a complexity analysis for the system when inductive definitions are self-recursive only and not mutually recursive.
- We have implemented the proposal in a prototype tool, called $S2S_{Lin}$, and tested it with SL-COMP 2019 benchmarks [36,37]. The experimental results show that $S2S_{Lin}$ is both effective and efficient when compared with the state-of-the-art solvers.

Organization The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Sect. 2 describes syntax of separation logic formulas and fragment SHLIDe. Sect. 3 gives an overview of the proposal. Sect. 4 elaborates the result, the novel cyclic proof system including an illustrative example. Sect. 5 shows the correctness. Sect. 6 presents the implementation and evaluation. Sect. 7 discusses related work. Finally, Sect. 8 concludes the work. Due to the space constraint, the missing proofs are available in Appendix.

2 Decidable Fragment SHLIDe

Subsection 2.1 presents syntax of separation logic formulae and recursive definitions of linear predicates and local properties. Subsection 2.2 shows semantics.

2.1 Separation Logic Formulas

Concrete heap models assume a fixed finite collection *Node*, a fixed finite collection *Fields*, a set *Loc* of locations (heap addresses), a set of non-address values *Val*, with the requirement that $Val \cap Loc = \emptyset$ (i.e., no pointer arithmetic). `null` is a special element of *Val*. We denote as \mathbb{Z} the set of integers whose elements are denoted as k and $\mathbb{Z} \subseteq Val$, and *Var* an infinite set of variables, \bar{v} a sequence of variables. Given \bar{v} , we denote as \bar{v}^S the sub-sequence of pointer-typed (i.e., non-integer type) variables.

Syntax Disjunctive formula Φ , symbolic heaps Δ , spatial formula κ , pure formula π , pointer (dis)equality ϕ , and formula in Presburger arithmetic α are as follows.

$$\begin{array}{lll} \Phi ::= \Delta \mid \Phi \vee \Phi & \Delta ::= \exists \bar{v}. (\kappa \wedge \pi) & \phi ::= v=v \mid v=\text{null} \\ \kappa ::= \text{emp} \mid x \mapsto c(f:v, \dots, f:v) \mid P(\bar{v}) \mid \kappa * \kappa & \alpha ::= a=a \mid a \leq a & \\ \pi ::= \text{true} \mid \alpha \mid \phi \mid \neg \pi \mid \exists v. \pi \mid \pi \wedge \pi & a ::= k \mid v \mid k \times a \mid a + a \mid -a & \end{array}$$

where $v \in Var$, $c \in Node$ and $f \in Fields$. The spatial formula κ may be conjoined by `emp` predicate, points-to predicates $x \mapsto c(f:v, \dots, f:v)$ and inductive predicates $P(\bar{v})$. We often discard field names f and use the short form $x \mapsto c(\bar{v})$. Note that $v_1 \neq v_2$ is the short form of $\neg(v_1 = v_2)$. E denotes for either a variable or `null`. $\Delta[E/v]$ denotes the formula obtained from Δ by substituting v by E . A symbolic heap is referred as a base, denoted as Δ^b , if it does not contain any occurrence of inductive predicates.

Inductive Definitions We write \mathcal{P} to denote a set of n defined predicates $\mathcal{P} = \{P_1, \dots, P_n\}$ in our system. In this work, we consider two types of local properties: transitivity (e.g., singly-linked lists where every singleton heaps contain the same value a) and ordering (e.g., trees being binary search trees). An inductive predicate is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pred } P(r, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \wedge sc = tg \\ &\vee \exists X_{tl}, \bar{Z}, sc'. r \mapsto c(X_{tl}, \bar{p}, u, sc') * \kappa' * P(X_{tl}, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg) \wedge r \neq F \wedge sc \diamond sc' + k \end{aligned}$$

where r is called the root parameter, F the target parameter, \bar{B} the borders, u the parameter for a transitivity property, sc and tg source and target, respectively, parameters of an order property, $r \mapsto c(X_{tl}, \bar{p}, u, sc') * \kappa'$ the matrix of the heaps, and $\diamond \in \{=, \geq, \leq\}$. (The extension for multiple local properties is straightforward.) Moreover, this definition is constrained by the following two conditions on heap connectivity and establishment.

Condition C1. In the recursive rule, $\bar{p} = \{\text{null}\} \cup \bar{Z}$. This condition implies that variables at fields of a points-to predicate are decided by its root variable. For instance, the following definition of singly-linked lists of even length does not satisfy this condition.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pred } \text{ell}(r, F, n_1, n_2) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \wedge n_1 = n_2 \\ &\vee \exists x_1, X, n_3. r \mapsto c_1(x_1) * x_1 \mapsto c_1(X) * \text{ell}(X, F, n_3, n_2) \wedge r \neq F \wedge n_1 = n_3 + 2 \end{aligned}$$

as n_3 and X are not field variables of the node pointed-to by r .

Condition C2. The matrix heap defines nested and connected list segments as:

$$\kappa' := Q(Z, U, \bar{Y}) \mid \kappa' * \kappa' \mid \text{emp}$$

where $Z \in \bar{p}$. Additionally, if $U \in \bar{Z}$ then the matrix κ' contains another inductive predicate $Q'(U, U', \bar{Y}')$. The restriction on connectivity could be precisely described via Gaifman graph like in [14,16]. If all definitions are not mutual recursion, we define $P \prec_P Q$ if at least one occurrence of predicate Q appears in the definition of P . We use \prec_P^* to denote the transitive closure of \prec_P .

Several definition examples are shown as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{pred } \mathbf{11}(r, F) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \vee \exists X_{tl}. r \mapsto c_1(X_{tl}) * \mathbf{11}(X_{tl}, F) \wedge r \neq F \\
\text{pred } \mathbf{n11}(r, F, B) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \\
&\vee \exists X_{tl}, Z. r \mapsto c_3(X_{tl}, Z) * \mathbf{11}(Z, B) * \mathbf{n11}(X_{tl}, F, B) \wedge r \neq F \\
\text{pred } P(r, F) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \vee \exists X_{tl}, Z. r \mapsto c_3(X_{tl}, Z) * Q(Z, F) * P(X_{tl}, F) \wedge r \neq F \\
\text{pred } Q(r, F) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \vee \exists X_{tl}, Z. r \mapsto c_3(X_{tl}, Z) * P(Z, F) * Q(X_{tl}, F) \wedge r \neq F \\
\text{pred } \mathbf{sk11}(r, F) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \vee \exists X_{tl}. r \mapsto c_4(X_{tl}, \mathbf{null}, \mathbf{null}) * \mathbf{sk11}(X_{tl}, F) \wedge r \neq F \\
\text{pred } \mathbf{sk12}(r, F) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \\
&\vee \exists X_{tl}, Z_1. r \mapsto c_4(Z_1, X_{tl}, \mathbf{null}) * \mathbf{sk11}(Z_1, X_{tl}) * \mathbf{sk12}(X_{tl}, F) \wedge r \neq F \\
\text{pred } \mathbf{sk13}(r, F) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \\
&\vee \exists X_{tl}, Z_1, Z_2. r \mapsto c_4(Z_1, Z_2, X_{tl}) * \mathbf{sk11}(Z_1, Z_2) * \mathbf{sk12}(Z_2, X_{tl}) * \mathbf{sk13}(X_{tl}, F) \wedge r \neq F \\
\text{pred } \mathbf{tree}(r, B) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = B \\
&\vee \exists r_l, r_r. r \mapsto c_t(r_l, r_r) * \mathbf{tree}(r_l, B) * \mathbf{tree}(r_r, B) \wedge r \neq B
\end{aligned}$$

$\mathbf{11}$ defines singly-linked lists, $\mathbf{n11}$ defines lists of acyclic lists, $\mathbf{sk11}$, $\mathbf{sk12}$ and $\mathbf{sk13}$ define skip-lists. P and Q are mutually nested lists. Finally, \mathbf{tree} defines binary trees. We extend predicate $\mathbf{11}$ with transitivity and order parameters to obtain predicate $\mathbf{11a}$ and $\mathbf{11s}$, respectively, as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{pred } \mathbf{11a}(r, F, a) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \vee \exists X_{tl}. r \mapsto c_2(X_{tl}, a) * \mathbf{11a}(X_{tl}, F, a) \wedge r \neq F \\
\text{pred } \mathbf{11s}(r, F, mi, ma) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \wedge ma = mi \\
&\vee \exists X_{tl}, mi_1. r \mapsto c_4(X_{tl}, mi_1) * \mathbf{11s}(X_{tl}, F, mi_1, ma) \wedge r \neq F \wedge mi \leq mi_1
\end{aligned}$$

Unfolding Given $\text{pred } P(\bar{t}) \equiv \Phi$ and a formula $P(\bar{v}) * \Delta$, then unfolding is the act to replace $P(\bar{v})$ by $\Phi[\bar{v}/\bar{t}]$. Further assume its recursive rule be

$$\exists \bar{w}. r \mapsto c(\bar{p}) * Q_1(\bar{v}_1) * \dots * Q_m(\bar{v}_m) * P(\bar{v}_0) \wedge \pi$$

then both $P(\bar{v}_0)[\bar{v}/\bar{t}]$ and $Q_i(\dots)$ is called a direct sub-term of $P(\bar{v})$. Obviously, the sub-term relation is transitive. We annotate a number, called unfolding number, for each occurrence of inductive predicates to denote the hierarchy of the sub-term relationships. In the unfolded formula, if $P(\bar{v}_0[\bar{v}/\bar{t}])^{k_1}$ is a direct sub-term of $P(\bar{v})^{k_2}$ like above, then $k_1 = k_2 + 1$. These unfolding numbers are important to construct cyclic proofs. When it is unambiguous, we discard the annotation of the unfolding number for simplicity.

2.2 Semantics

The semantics is given by a relation: $s, h \models \Phi$ that forces the stack s and heap h to satisfy the constraint Φ where $h \in \text{Heaps}$, $s \in \text{Stacks}$, and Φ is a formula. Stack and heap abstractions are defined as (assume that every data structure contains at most N field):

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Heaps} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{Loc} \rightarrow_{\text{fin}} (\text{Node} \rightarrow (\text{Fields} \rightarrow \text{Val} \cup \text{Loc})^N) \\
\text{Stacks} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{Var} \rightarrow \text{Val} \cup \text{Loc}
\end{aligned}$$

$s, h \models \mathbf{emp}$	iff $dom(h)=\emptyset$
$s, h \models v \mapsto c(f_i : v_i)$	iff $dom(h)=\{s(v)\}, h(s(v))=g, g(c, f_i)=s(v_i)$
$s, h \models \mathbf{P}(\bar{t})$	iff $\exists m. s, h \models \mathbf{P}^m(\bar{t})$
$s, h \models \mathbf{P}^0(r, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)$	iff $s(r)=s(F) \wedge s(sc)=s(tg) \wedge h=\emptyset$
$s, h \models \mathbf{P}^{k+1}(r, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)$	iff $s, h \models \exists X_{tl}, \bar{Z}, sc'. r \mapsto c(X_{tl}, \bar{p}, u, sc') * \kappa' * \mathbf{P}^k(X_{tl}, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg) \wedge r \neq F \wedge sc \diamond sc' + k$
$s, h \models \kappa_1 * \kappa_2$	iff $\exists h_1, h_2. h_1 \# h_2$ and $h=h_1 \cdot h_2,$ $s, h_1 \models \kappa_1$ and $s, h_2 \models \kappa_2$
$s, h \models \mathbf{true}$	iff always
$s, h \models \exists v. (\kappa \wedge \pi)$	iff $\exists \alpha. s[v \mapsto \alpha], h \models \kappa$ and $s[v \mapsto \alpha] \models \pi$
$s, h \models \Phi_1 \vee \Phi_2$	iff $s, h \models \Phi_1$ or $s, h \models \Phi_2$

Fig. 1: Semantics.

The semantics is shown in Fig. 1 where $dom(g)$ is the domain of function g , $h_1 \# h_2$ denotes disjoint heaps h_1 and h_2 i.e., $dom(h_1) \cap dom(h_2) = \emptyset$, and $h_1 \cdot h_2$ denotes the union of two disjoint heaps. If s is a stack, $v \in Var$, and $\alpha \in Val \cup Loc$, we write $s[v \mapsto \alpha] \equiv s$ if $v \in dom(s)$, otherwise $s[v \mapsto \alpha] \equiv s \cup \{(v, \alpha)\}$. Semantics of non-heap (pure) formulas depends on stack valuations only and is omitted for simplicity. The interpretation of an inductive predicate $\mathbf{P}(\bar{t})$ is based on the least fixed point semantics.

Entailment $\Delta \models \Delta'$ holds iff for all s and h , we have if $s, h \models \Delta$ then $s, h \models \Delta'$.

3 Entailment Problem & Overview

An entailment, denoted as e , is syntactically formalized as: $\Delta_a \vdash \Delta_c$ where Δ_a and Δ_c are quantifier-free formulas whose syntax are defined in the preceding section. The meaning of this formalism is that $\Delta_a \vdash \Delta_c$ is valid iff $\Delta_a \models \Delta_c$ holds.

Throughout this work, we consider the following problem.

PROBLEM: QF_ENT-SL. INPUT: $\Delta_a \equiv \kappa_a \wedge \pi_a$ and $\Delta_c \equiv \kappa_c \wedge \pi_c$ where $FV(\Delta_c) \subseteq FV(\Delta_a) \cup \{\mathbf{null}\}$. QUESTION: Is $\Delta_a \vdash \Delta_c$ valid?

Overview Central to our approach is a decision procedure that is used to construct cyclic reduction trees for an entailment. The procedure searches for a cyclic proof of the input through a set of inference rules. Each inference rule is of the following form:

$$\text{PR}_0 \frac{e_1 \quad \dots \quad e_n}{e} \text{ cond}$$

where entailment e (called the conclusion) is reduced to entailments e_1, \dots, e_n (called the premises) through inference rule PR_0 given that the *side conditions* cond holds.

A cyclic proof tree \mathcal{T}_i is a tuple (V, E, \mathcal{C}) such that

- V is a finite set of nodes representing entailments derived during the proof search;
- A directed edges $(e, \text{PR}, e') \in E$ (where e' is a child of e) means that the premise e' is derived from the conclusion e via inference rule PR . For instance, suppose that the rule PR_0 above has been applied, then the following n edges are generated: $(e, \text{PR}_0, e_1), \dots, (e, \text{PR}_0, e_n)$;

- and \mathcal{C} is a partial relation which captures back-links in the proof tree. If $\mathcal{C}(e_c \rightarrow e_b, \sigma)$ holds, then e_b is linked back to its ancestor e_c through the substitution σ (where e_b is referred as a *bud* and e_c is referred as a *companion*). In particular, e_c is of the form: $\Delta \vdash \Delta'$ and e_b is of the form: $\Delta_1 \wedge \pi \vdash \Delta'_1$ where $\Delta \equiv \Delta_1 \sigma$ and $\Delta' \equiv \Delta'_1 \sigma$.

A leaf node is marked as closed if it is evaluated as valid or invalid, or it is linked back. Otherwise, it is marked as open. A proof tree is *invalid* if it contains at least one invalid leaf node. It is a *pre-proof* if all its leaf nodes are either valid or linked back. A pre-proof is a cyclic proof if a global soundness condition is imposed in the tree. Intuitively, this soundness condition requires that for every $\mathcal{C}(e_c \rightarrow e_b, \sigma)$, there exist inductive predicates $P(\bar{t}_1)$ in e_c and $Q(\bar{t}_2)$ in e_b such that $Q(\bar{t}_2)$ is a subterm of $P(\bar{t}_1)$.

Definition 1 (Trace) Let \mathcal{T}_i be a pre-proof of $\Delta_a \vdash \Delta_c$; $(\Delta_{a_i} \vdash \Delta_{c_i})_{i \geq 0}$ be a path of \mathcal{T}_i . A trace following $(\Delta_{a_i} \vdash \Delta_{c_i})_{i \geq 0}$ is a sequence $(\alpha_i)_{i \geq 0}$ such that each α_i (for all $i \geq 0$) is a subformula of Δ_{a_i} containing predicate $P(\bar{t})^u$, and either:

- α_{i+1} is the subformula $P(\bar{t})^u \in \Delta_{a_{i+1}}$.
- or α_{i+1} is a subformula $\kappa * Q(\bar{v})^k \wedge \pi \in \Delta_{a_{i+1}}$ where $\kappa * Q(\bar{v})^k \wedge \pi$ is the recursive rule in the definition of $P(\bar{t})^u$ and $k > u$. i is called a *progressing point* of the trace.

Definition 2 (Cyclic proof) A pre-proof \mathcal{T}_i of $\Delta_a \vdash \Delta_c$ is a cyclic proof if, for every infinite path $(\Delta_{a_i} \vdash \Delta_{c_i})_{i \geq 0}$ of \mathcal{T}_i , there is a tail of the path $p = (\Delta_{a_i} \vdash \Delta_{c_i})_{i \geq n}$ such that there is a trace following p which has infinitely progressing points.

Theorem 1 (Soundness [5]). If there is a cyclic proof of $\Delta_a \vdash \Delta_c$, then $\Delta_a \models \Delta_c$.

4 Cyclic Entailment Procedure

In this section, we present our main proposal, entailment procedure ω -ENT with the proposed inference rules (subsection 4.1), and an illustrative example in subsection 4.2.

4.1 Proof Search

For linear proofs, we introduce a normal form of entailment (NF for short) in which unfolding a predicate symbol in the RHS always obtains one disjunct. ω -ENT is presented in Fig. 2. ω -ENT takes e_0 as input and produces a decision which is valid or invalid. Initially, for every $P(\bar{v})^k \in e_0$, k is reset to 0. The overall idea of ω -ENT is to iteratively reduce e_0 into a cyclic proof tree \mathcal{T}_n which represents

Decision Procedure ω -ENT	
input: e_0	output: valid or invalid
1:	$i \leftarrow 0; \mathcal{T}_i \leftarrow e_0;$
2:	while true do
3:	$\mathcal{T}_i^1 \leftarrow \text{normalize}(\mathcal{T}_i);$
4:	$\mathcal{T}_i^2 \leftarrow \text{evaluate}(\mathcal{T}_i^1);$
5:	$\mathcal{T}_i^3 \leftarrow \text{link_back}_e(\mathcal{T}_i^2);$
6:	$(\text{res}, e_i) \leftarrow \text{is_closed}(\mathcal{T}_i^3);$
7:	if res=valid then return valid;
8:	if res=invalid then return invalid;
9:	$\mathcal{T}_{i+1} \leftarrow \text{reduce}(\mathcal{T}_i^3, e_i); i \leftarrow i+1;$
10:	end

Fig. 2: Proof Search.

all solvable entailments using the proposed set of inference rules. Inference rules are classified into three groups: normalization rules, evaluation rules and reduction rules. ω -ENT works as follows. (i) Every leaf node is applied with normalization rules (line 3) until it is in NF prior to being applied with either reduction rules to evaluate (line 4), or reduce it into multiple sub-goals (line 9) or back-link generation (line 5). (ii) A leaf node in NF which could not be applied with any reduction rules (is stuck) is classified as `invalid` and any model satisfying its LHS is a counter-model. (iii) A leaf node which could be applied with an axiom rule is classified as `valid`. An entailment is in the normal form if its LHS is in NF. To define the normalization form, we write $op(E)$ to denote for either $E \mapsto c(\bar{v})$ or $P(E, F, \bar{B}, \bar{v})$. Furthermore, the guard $G(op(E))$ is defined by: $G(E \mapsto c(\bar{v})) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{true}$ and $G(P(E, F, \bar{B}, \bar{v})) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} E \neq F$.

Definition 3 (Normal Form) *A formula $\kappa \wedge \phi \wedge a$ is in normal form if:*

- | | |
|---|----------------------------|
| 1. $op(E) \in \kappa$ implies $G(op(E)) \in \phi$ | 4. $E_1 = E_2 \notin \phi$ |
| 2. $op(E) \in \kappa$ implies $E \neq \text{null} \in \phi$ | 5. $E \neq E \notin \phi$ |
| 3. $op_1(E_1) * op_2(E_2) \in \kappa$ implies $E_1 \neq E_2 \in \phi$ | 6. a is satisfiable |

If Δ is in NF and for any $s, h \models \Delta$, then $dom(h)$ is uniquely defined by s .

In the rest, we discuss the inference rules and the auxiliary procedures in details.

Procedure is_closed This procedure examines the following three cases.

1. First, if all leaf nodes are marked closed and none of them is `invalid` then `is_closed` returns `valid` with a pre-proof. After that, at line 7, ω -ENT returns `valid`.
2. Secondly, `is_closed` returns `invalid` if there exists an open leaf node $e_i : \Delta \vdash \Delta'$ in NF such that one of the four following conditions holds:
 - (a) e_i could not be applied by any inference rule.
 - (b) there exists a predicate $op_1(E) \in \Delta$ such that $op_2(E) \notin \Delta'$ and one of the following conditions holds:
 - either $P(E', E, \dots)$ or $E' \mapsto c(E, \dots)$ are in both sides
 - both $P(E', E, \dots) \notin \Delta$ and $E' \mapsto c(E, \dots) \notin \Delta$
 - (c) there exists a predicate $op_1(E) \in \Delta'$ such that $G(op_1(E)) \in \Delta$ and $op_2(E) \notin \Delta$.
 - (d) there exist $x \mapsto c_1(\bar{v}_1) \in \Delta$, $x \mapsto c_2(\bar{v}_2) \in \Delta'$ such that either $c_1 \neq c_2$ or $\bar{v}_1 \neq \bar{v}_2$. After that, at line 8, ω -ENT returns `invalid`.
3. Lastly, there exists an open leaf node e_i that could be applied by an inference rule, `is_closed` returns the pair (`unknown`, e_i). At line 9, ω -ENT applies the rule into e_i .

Normalization The normalization rules are presented in Fig. 3. *Our system applies these rules into an entailment exhaustively to transform it into the NF.* Given an inductive predicate $P(E, F, \dots)$, rule `EXM` excludes the middle by doing case analysis for the predicate between base-case (i.e., $E = F$) and recursive-case (i.e., $E \neq F$). The normalization rule `≠null` follows the following facts.

$$E \mapsto c(-) \Rightarrow E \neq \text{null} \quad P(E, F, -) \wedge E \neq F \Rightarrow E \neq \text{null}$$

Similarly, the normalization rule `≠*` follows the following facts.

$$\begin{aligned} x \mapsto - * y \mapsto - &\Rightarrow x \neq y & x \mapsto - * P(y, F, -) \wedge y \neq F &\Rightarrow x \neq y \\ P_i(x, F_1, -) * P_j(y, F_2, -) \wedge x \neq F_1 \wedge y \neq F_2 &\Rightarrow x \neq y \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{SUBST} \frac{\Delta[E/x] \vdash \Delta'[E/x]}{\Delta \wedge x=E \vdash \Delta'} \quad \text{EXM} \frac{\Delta \wedge E_1=E_2 \vdash \Delta' \quad \Delta \wedge E_1 \neq E_2 \vdash \Delta'}{\Delta \vdash \Delta'} \quad \frac{E_1 \neq E_2 \quad E_1=E_2, E_1 \neq E_2 \notin \pi}{FV(E_1, E_2) \subseteq (FV(\Delta) \cup FV(\Delta'))^S} \\
\\
=_{\text{L}} \frac{\Delta \vdash \Delta'}{\Delta \wedge E=E \vdash \Delta'} \quad \text{LBase} \frac{(\kappa \wedge \pi)[tg/sc] \vdash \Delta'[tg/sc]}{P(E, E, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg) * \kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \Delta'} \\
\\
\neq_{\text{null}} \frac{op(E) * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge G(op(E)) \wedge E \neq \text{null} \vdash \Delta'}{op(E) * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge G(op(E)) \vdash \Delta'} \quad E \neq \text{null} \notin \pi \\
\\
\neq_* \frac{op_1(E_1) * op_2(E_2) * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge E_1 \neq E_2 \vdash \Delta'}{op_1(E_1) * op_2(E_2) * \kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \Delta'} \quad E_1 \neq E_2 \notin \pi \text{ and } G(op_1(E_1)), G(op_2(E_2)) \in \pi
\end{array}$$

Fig. 3: Normalization Rules

Evaluation and Reduction Those axiom rules EMP, INCONSISTENCY and IDENTITY presented in Fig. 4 are evaluation rules. If they are applied into a leaf node, the node is evaluated as valid and marked as closed. The remaining rules in Fig. 4 are used to reduce an entailment in NF. To simplify the presentation, the unfoldings in rules RInd and LInd are applied with the following definition of inductive predicates:

$$\begin{aligned}
P(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge x=F \wedge sc=tg \\
&\vee \exists X, sc', d_1, d_2. x \mapsto c(X, d_1, d_2, u, sc) * Q_1(d_1, B) * Q_2(d_2, X) * P(X, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg) \wedge \pi_0
\end{aligned}$$

where $B \in \bar{B}$, the matrix κ' contains two nested predicates Q_1 and Q_2 , and the heap cell $c \in \text{Node}$ is defined as `data c{c next; c1 down1; c2 down2; τs scdata; τu udata}` where $c_1, c_2 \in \text{Node}$, `down1`, `down2` fields are for the nested predicates in the matrix heaps, `udata` field is for the transitivity data, and `scdata` field are for ordering data. The formalism of these rules for general form of the matrix heaps κ' is presented in App. A.

`=R` and HYPOTHESIS eliminate pure constraints in the RHS. In rule `*`, $\Pi(\bar{v}, \pi)$ returns the maximal sub-formula of π that contains variables in \bar{v} . And $\text{roots}(\kappa)$ is defined inductively as: $\text{roots}(\text{emp}) \equiv \{\}$, $\text{roots}(r \mapsto _) \equiv \{r\}$, $\text{roots}(P(r, F, \dots)) \equiv \{r\}$ and $\text{roots}(\kappa_1 * \kappa_2) \equiv \text{roots}(\kappa_1) \cup \text{roots}(\kappa_2)$. This rule is applied in three ways. First, it is applied into an entailment which is of the form $\kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa \wedge \pi'$. It matches and discards the identified heap predicates between the two sides so as to generate a premise with empty heaps. As a result, this premise may be applied with the axiom rule EMP. Secondly, it is applied into an entailment whose LHS is a base formula e.g., $x_1 \mapsto c_1(\bar{v}_1) * \dots * x_n \mapsto c_n(\bar{v}_n) \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa' \wedge \pi'$. For each points-to predicate $x_i \mapsto c_i(\bar{v}_i) \in \kappa'$, ω -ENT searches for one points-to predicate $x_j \mapsto c_j(\bar{v}_j)$ in the LHS such that $x_j \mapsto c_j(\bar{v}_j) \equiv x_i \mapsto c_i(\bar{v}_i)$. Similarly, for each occurrence of inductive predicates $P(r, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)$ in the RHS, ω -ENT searches for a points-to predicate $r \mapsto _$ in the LHS such that rule RInd could be applied. If any of these searches fails, ω -ENT decides the conclusion as invalid. Lastly, it is applied into an entailment that is of the form $\Delta_1 * \Delta \vdash \Delta_2 * \Delta'$ where either $\Delta_1 \vdash \Delta_2$ or $\Delta \vdash \Delta'$ could be linked back into an internal node.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{IDENTITY} \frac{}{\Delta \vdash \Delta} \quad \text{EMP} \frac{}{\text{emp} \wedge \pi \vdash \text{emp} \wedge \text{true}} \quad \text{INCONSISTENCY} \frac{}{\kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \Delta} \quad \pi \models \text{false} \\
\\
\text{R-SUBST} \frac{\kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa' \wedge \pi' [tg/sc]}{\kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa' \wedge \pi' \wedge tg=sc} \quad \kappa' \neq \text{emp or} \quad \pi' \neq \text{true} \quad \text{RBase} \frac{\Delta_1 \vdash \kappa_2 \wedge \pi_2 \wedge tg=sc}{\Delta_1 \vdash \text{P}(E, E, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg) * \kappa_2 \wedge \pi_2} \\
\\
* \frac{\kappa_1 \wedge \Pi(FV(\kappa_1), \pi) \vdash \kappa_2 \wedge \Pi(FV(\kappa_2), \pi') \quad \kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa' \wedge \pi' \quad \text{roots}(\kappa_1) \cap \text{roots}(\kappa) = \emptyset}{\kappa_1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa_2 * \kappa' \wedge \pi'} \quad \text{FV}(\kappa_1) \subseteq \text{FV}(\kappa_2) \cup \{\text{null}\} \\
\text{FV}(\kappa \wedge \pi) \subseteq \text{FV}(\kappa' \wedge \pi') \cup \{\text{null}\} \\
\text{=R} \frac{\kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa' \wedge \pi'}{\kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa' \wedge \pi' \wedge E=E} \quad \text{HYPOTHESIS} \frac{\Delta \wedge \pi \vdash \Delta'}{\Delta \wedge \pi \vdash \Delta' \wedge \pi'} \quad \pi \models \pi' \\
\\
\text{RInd} \frac{x \mapsto c(X, E_1, E_2, u, sc') * \kappa_1 \wedge \pi_1 \wedge x \neq F \quad \vdash x \mapsto c(X, E_1, E_2, u, sc') * \text{Q}_1(E_1, B) * \text{Q}_2(E_2, X) * \text{P}(X, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg) * \kappa_2 \wedge \pi_2 \wedge \pi_0}{x \mapsto c(X, E_1, E_2, u, sc') * \kappa_1 \wedge \pi_1 \wedge x \neq F \vdash \text{P}(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg) * \kappa_2 \wedge \pi_2} \dagger \\
\dagger: x \mapsto c(X, E_1, E_2, u, sc') \notin \kappa_2 \quad \ddagger: x \mapsto c_i(l, r, u, sc) \notin \kappa_2 \\
\\
\text{LInd} \frac{x \mapsto c(X, E_1, E_2, u, sc') * \text{Q}_1(E_1, B)^{k+1} * \text{Q}_2(E_2, X)^{k+1} * \text{P}(X, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg)^{k+1} * \Delta_1 \wedge x \neq F_3 \wedge \pi_0 \vdash \text{Q}(x, F_3, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa_2 \wedge \pi_2}{\text{P}(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)^k * \Delta_1 \wedge x \neq F_3 \vdash \text{Q}(x, F_3, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa_2 \wedge \pi_2} \# \\
\# : \text{P}(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg) \notin \kappa_2
\end{array}$$

Fig. 4: Reduction Rules

Rule LInd unfolds the inductive predicates in the LHS. We notice that every LHS of entailments in this rule also captures the unfolding numbers for subterm relationship and generates the progressing point in the proofs. These numbers are essential for our system to construct cyclic proofs. This rule is applied in a breadth-first manner i.e., if there are more than one occurrences of inductive predicates in the LHS that could be applied by this rule, the one with the smallest unfolding number is chosen. We emphasize that the last five rules still work well when the predicate in the RHS contains only a subset of the local properties wrt. the predicate in the LHS.

Back-Link Generation Procedure `link.backe` generates a back-link as follows. In a pre-proof, given a path corresponding to a back-link, say $\Delta_1, \Delta_2, \dots, \Delta_m$ where Δ_1 is a companion and Δ_m a bud, then Δ_1 is in NF and of the following form:

- $\Delta_1 \equiv \text{P}(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)^{k_1} * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq \text{null} \vdash \text{Q}(x, F_2, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa' \wedge \pi'$.
- Δ_2 is obtained from applying LInd into Δ_1 . Δ_2 is of the form:

$$\begin{array}{l}
x \mapsto c(X, \bar{p}, u, sc) * \kappa' * \text{P}(X, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg)^{k_1+1} * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge \pi_1 \\
\vdash \text{Q}(x, F_2, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa' \wedge \pi'
\end{array}$$

- $\Delta_3, \dots, \Delta_{m-4}$ are obtained from applications of normalization rules in order to normalize the LHS of Δ_2 due to the presence of κ' . We note that as the roots of inductive predicates in κ' are fresh variables, the applications of the normalization

rules above do not affect the RHS of Δ_2 . That means RHS of $\Delta_3, \dots, \Delta_{m-4}$ are the same with the RHS of Δ_2 . As a result, Δ_{m-4} is of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} & x \mapsto c(X, \bar{p}, u, sc) * \kappa_1'' * P(X, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg)^{k_1+1} * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge \pi_1 \wedge \pi_2 \\ & \vdash Q(x, F_2, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa' \wedge \pi' \end{aligned}$$

where κ_1'' may be emp and π_2 is a conjunction of disequalities coming from EXM.

– Δ_{m-3} is obtained from application of EXM over x and F_2 and of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} & x \mapsto c(X, \bar{p}, u, sc) * \kappa_1'' * P(X, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg)^{k_1+1} * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge \pi_1 \wedge \pi_2 \\ & \wedge x \neq F_2 \vdash Q(x, F_2, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa' \wedge \pi' \end{aligned}$$

(For the case $x = F_2$, the rule EXM is kept applying until either $F \equiv F_2$, that is two sides are reaching the end of the same heap segment, or it is stuck.)

– Δ_{m-2} is obtained from application of RInd and is of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} & x \mapsto c(X, \bar{p}, u, sc) * \kappa_1'' * P(X, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg)^{k_1+1} * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge \pi_1 \wedge \pi_2 \\ & \wedge x \neq F_2 \vdash x \mapsto c(X, \bar{p}, u, sc) * \kappa_2'' * Q(X, F_2, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa' \wedge \pi' \wedge \pi_2' \end{aligned}$$

– Δ_{m-1} is obtained from application of HYPOTHESIS to eliminate π_2' (otherwise, it is stuck) and is of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} & x \mapsto c(X, \bar{p}, u, sc) * \kappa_1'' * P(X, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg)^{k_1+1} * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge \pi_1 \wedge \pi_2 \\ & \wedge x \neq F_2 \vdash x \mapsto c(X, \bar{p}, u, sc) * \kappa_2'' * Q(X, F_2, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa' \wedge \pi' \end{aligned}$$

– Δ_m is obtained from application of $*$ and is of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} & P(X, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg)^{k_1+1} * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge \pi_1 \wedge \pi_2 \wedge x \neq F_2 \\ & \vdash Q(X, F_2, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa' \wedge \pi' \end{aligned}$$

Δ_m is linked to Δ_1 through the substitution is $\sigma \equiv [x/X, sc/sc']$ after weakening some pure constraints in its LHS.

4.2 Illustrative Example

We illustrate our system through the following example:

$$e_0: \text{11n}(x, \text{null}, mi, ma)^0 \wedge x \neq \text{null} \vdash \text{11s}(x, \text{null}, mi, ma)$$

where the sorted linked-lists `11s` is defined in Sect. 2.1 and `11n` defines singly-linked lists whose nodes contain increasing values and values of two continuous nodes are different by one. Particularly, predicate `11n` is defined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pred } \text{11n}(r, F, mi, ma) & \equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \wedge ma = mi \\ & \vee \exists X_{tl}, mi_1. r \mapsto c_4(X_{tl}, mi_1) * \text{11n}(X_{tl}, F, mi_1, ma) \wedge r \neq F \wedge mi = mi_1 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

Since the LHS is stronger than the RHS, this entailment is valid. Our system could generate the cyclic proof (shown in Fig. 5) to prove the validity of e_0 . In the following,

Fig. 5: Cyclic Proof of e_0 .

we present step-by-step how the proof was created. Firstly, e_0 , which is in NF, is applied with rule $LInd$ to unfold predicate $lln(x, null, mi, ma)^0$ and obtain e_1 as:

$$e_1: x \mapsto c_4(X, m') * lln(X, null, m', ma)^1 \wedge x \neq null \wedge mi = m' - 1 \vdash ll s(x, null, mi, ma)$$

As can be seen, the unfolding number of the recursive predicate lln in the LHS is increased by 1. Next, our system normalizes e_1 by applying rule EXM into X and $null$ to generate two children e_2 and e_3 as follows.

$$e_2: x \mapsto c_4(X, m') * lln(X, null, m', ma)^1 \wedge x \neq null \wedge mi = m' - 1 \wedge X = null \vdash ll s(x, null, mi, ma)$$

$$e_3: x \mapsto c_4(X, m') * lln(X, null, m', ma)^1 \wedge x \neq null \wedge mi = m' - 1 \wedge X \neq null \vdash ll s(x, null, mi, ma)$$

For the left child, it applies normalization rules to obtain e_4 (substitute X by $null$) and then e_5 (by $LBase$) as:

$$e_4: x \mapsto c_4(null, m') * lln(null, null, m', ma)^1 \wedge x \neq null \wedge mi = m' - 1 \vdash ll s(x, null, mi, ma)$$

$$e_5: x \mapsto c_4(null, ma) \wedge x \neq null \wedge mi = ma - 1 \vdash ll s(x, null, mi, ma)$$

Now, e_5 is in NF. Our system applies reduction rule $RInd$ and then $RBase$ to discard the predicate lls in the RHS as:

$$e_6: x \mapsto c_4(null, ma) \wedge x \neq null \wedge mi = ma - 1 \vdash x \mapsto c_4(null, ma) * ll s(null, null, ma, ma) \wedge mi \leq ma$$

$$e_{6'}: x \mapsto c_4(null, ma) \wedge x \neq null \wedge mi = ma - 1 \vdash x \mapsto c_4(null, ma) \wedge mi \leq ma$$

$$e_7: x \mapsto c_4(null, ma) \wedge x \neq null \wedge mi = ma - 1 \vdash x \mapsto c_4(null, ma)$$

After that, as $mi = ma - 1 \Rightarrow mi \leq ma$, $e_{6'}$ is applied with $HYPOTHESIS$ to obtain e_7 . As the LHS of e_7 is in NF and a base formula, it is sound and complete to apply rule $*$ to have e_8 as: $emp \wedge x \neq null \wedge mi = ma - 1 \vdash emp$. By EMP , e_8 is decided as valid. For the right branch of the proof, e_3 is applied with rule $\neq*$ and then $RInd$ to obtain e_9 :

$$e_9: x \mapsto c_4(X, m') * lln(X, null, m', ma)^1 \wedge x \neq null \wedge mi = m' - 1 \wedge X \neq null \wedge x \neq X \vdash x \mapsto c_4(X, m') * ll s(X, null, m', ma) \wedge mi \leq m'$$

After that, e_9 is applied with HYPOTHESIS to eliminate the pure constraint in the RHS:

$$e_{10}: x \mapsto c_4(X, m') * \text{lln}(X, \text{null}, m', ma)^1 \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge mi = m' - 1 \wedge X \neq \text{null} \wedge x \neq X \\ \vdash x \mapsto c_4(X, m') * \text{lls}(X, \text{null}, m', ma)$$

e_0 is applied with $*$ to obtain e_{11} and e_{12} as follows.

$$e_{11}: x \mapsto c_4(X, m') \vdash x \mapsto c_4(X, m') \\ e_{12}: \text{lln}(X, \text{null}, m', ma)^1 \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge mi = m' - 1 \wedge X \neq \text{null} \wedge x \neq X \\ \vdash \text{lls}(X, \text{null}, m', ma)$$

e_{11} is valid by IDENTITY. e_{12} is successfully linked back to e_0 to form a pre-proof as

$$(\text{lln}(X, \text{null}, m', ma)^1 \wedge X \neq \text{null})[x/X, mi/m'] \vdash \text{lls}(X, \text{null}, m', ma)[x/X, mi/m']$$

is identical to e_0 . Since $\text{lln}(X, \text{null}, m', ma)^1$ in e_{12} is the subterm of $\text{lln}(x, \text{null}, mi, ma)^0$ in e_0 , our system decided that e_0 is valid with the cyclic proof presented in Fig. 5.

5 Correctness

We describe soundness, termination and completeness of ω -ENT. First, we need to show the invariant about the quantifier-free entailments of our system.

Corollary 1. *Every entailments derived by ω -ENT are quantifier-free.*

The following lemma shows that ω -ENT is locally sound.

Lemma 1 (Local Soundness). *The proposed inference rules are sound.*

As every back-link generated contains at least one pair of inductive predicate occurrences in a subterm relationship, the global soundness condition holds in our system.

Lemma 2 (Global Soundness). *A pre-proof derived is indeed a cyclic proof.*

The termination relies on the number of premises/entailments generated by rule $*$. As the number of inductive symbols and their arities are finite, there is a finite number of equivalent classes of these entailments in which any two entailments in the same class are equivalent under some substitution and linked back together. Therefore, the number of premises generated by rule $*$ is finite under consideration of back-link generation.

Lemma 3. *ω -ENT is terminating.*

In the following, we show the complexity analysis when the system of inductive definitions is not mutually recursive. Particularly, Suppose that \mathcal{P} contains n definitions, M is the maximum number of occurrences of inductive predicates among the LHS of the input entailment and those definitions in \mathcal{P} , and m is the maximum number of variables among the input entailment and definition rules. Then, we show that every occurrence of inductive predicates in the LHS is unfolded at most once.

Lemma 4 (Non-Mutual). *Given any entailment $P(\bar{v})^k * \Delta_a \vdash \Delta_c$, then $0 \leq k \leq n$.*

The complexity of ω -ENT is defined as follows.

Proposition 1 (Non-Mutual Complexity). ω -ENT runs in $\mathcal{O}(n^5 m^2 M^{n+1})$.

Our completeness proofs are shown in two steps. First, we show the proofs for an entailment whose LHS is a base formula. Secondly, we show the correctness when the LHS contains inductive predicates. In the following, we first define the base formulas of the LHS derived by ω -ENT from occurrences of inductive predicates. Based on that, we define bad models to capture counter-model of invalid entailments.

Definition 4 (SHLIDe Base) Given κ , define $\bar{\kappa}$ as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{P(E, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} E \mapsto c(F, E_1, E_2, u, tg) * \overline{Q_1(E_1, B)} * \overline{Q_2(E_2, F)} \wedge \pi_0 \\ \overline{E \mapsto c(\bar{v})} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} E \mapsto c(\bar{v}) \quad \overline{\text{emp}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{emp} \quad \overline{\kappa_1 * \kappa_2} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \overline{\kappa_1} * \overline{\kappa_2} \end{aligned}$$

The definition for general definitions of predicates with arbitrary matrix heaps is presented in App. A. As our procedure terminates, the definition above terminates in a finite number of steps. In a pre-proof, these SHLIDe base formulas $\bar{\kappa}$ of the LHS of an entailment are obtained in paths starting from root to a companion, and then to the corresponding bud prior to following the back-link to come back the companion and finally exiting at a path leading to an invalid leaf.

Lemma 5. If $\kappa \wedge \pi$ is in NF then $\bar{\kappa} \wedge \pi$ is in NF, and $\bar{\kappa} \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa$ is valid.

In other words, $\bar{\kappa} \wedge \pi$ is an under-approximation of $\kappa \wedge \pi$; invalidity of $\bar{\kappa} \wedge \pi \vdash \Delta'$ implies invalidity of $\kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \Delta'$.

Definition 5 (Bad Model) The bad model for $\bar{\kappa} \wedge \phi \wedge a$ in NF is obtained by assigning

- a distinct non-null value to each variable in $FV(\bar{\kappa} \wedge \phi)$; and
- a value to each variable in $FV(a)$ such that a is satisfiable.

Lemma 6 (Local Completeness).

1. All inference rules except rule $*$ are complete.
2. Rule $*$ is complete when the conclusion is in NF.

The following lemma states the correctness of procedure `is_closed` for cases 2(b-d).

Lemma 7 (Stuck Invalidity). Given $\kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \Delta'$ in NF, it is invalid if procedure `is_closed` returns invalid for cases 2(b-d).

A bad model of the $\bar{\kappa} \wedge \pi$ is a counter-model. Cases 2b) and 2c) show that the heaps of bad models are not connected and thus accordingly to conditions **C1** and **C2**, any model of the LHS could not be a model of the RHS. Case 2d) shows that heaps of the two sides could not be matched. Now, we show the correctness of Case 2(a) of procedure `is_closed` and invalidity is preserved during the proof search in ω -ENT.

Proposition 2 (Global Completeness). ω -ENT is complete.

Theorem 2. ω -ENT is a decision procedure.

Table 1: Experimental Results on Entailments

Tool	<i>qf_shls_entl</i>			<i>qf_shlid_entl</i>			<i>qf_shlid2_entl</i>		
	invalid (122)	valid (174)	Time (296)	invalid (24)	valid (36)	Time (60)	invalid (14)	valid (13)	Time (27)
SLS	12	174	507m42s	2	35	133m28s	0	11	97m54s
Spen	122	174	10.78s	14	13	3.44s	8	2	1.69s
Cyclist _{SL}	0	58	1520m5s	0	24	360m38s	0	3	240m3s
Harrsh	39	116	425m19s	18	27	53m56s	8	7	156m45s
Songbird	12	174	237m25s	2	35	40m38s	0	12	47m11s
S2S _{Lin}	122	174	6.22s	24	36	0.96s	14	13	1.20s

6 Implementation and Evaluation

We have implemented the proposal in a tool, called `S2SLin`, using OCaml. We made use of Z3 [13] as a SMT solver for the linear arithmetic. We have evaluated `S2SLin` on benchmarks taken from SL-COMP 2019 [37], a competition of separation logic solvers. All experiments were performed on a machine with Intel Core i7-6700 CPU 3.4Gh and 8GB RAM. The CPU timeout is 600 seconds.

We conducted the experiments over benchmarks in two divisions of SL-COMP 2019, *qf_shls_entl* and *qf_shlid_entl*, and one fresh division which has not been integrated into the competition. All these problems are written in SMT 2.6 format [37] and semantically in SHLIDe. Particularly, entailments in *qf_shls_entl* (which were randomly generated by the authors in [30]) contain singly-linked lists. Entailments in *qf_shlid_entl* (which were mostly handcrafted by the authors in [14]) include singly-linked lists, doubly-linked lists, lists of singly-linked lists or skip lists. In the later division, for any two different predicates P, Q in the system of definitions, either $P \prec_P^* Q$ or $Q \prec_P^* P$. In the third division, we introduce new benchmarks where in the system of definitions there exist two predicates P, Q such that $P \not\prec_P^* Q$ and P may semantically equivalent to Q . We also compared `S2SLin` against state-of-the-art tools like `CyclistSL` [5], `Spen` [14], `Songbird` [38], `SLS` [39] and `Harrsh` [23]. We did not include `Cycomp` [40] as these benchmarks are beyond its decidable fragment.. For each division, we report the number of correct (`invalid`, `valid`) outputs and time (in minutes and seconds) taken by each tool. We note that in these experiments we made use of the pre-processing tool of the competition [37] to transform the SMT inputs into the corresponding formats of the tools before evaluating them.

The experimental results are reported in Table 1. In this table, the first column presents the name of tools. The next three columns show the results of the first division including the number of correct `invalid` outputs, the number of correct `valid` outputs and the time taken (where m for minutes and s for seconds), respectively. In the third row, the number between each pair of bracket (...) shows the number of problems in the corresponding column. Similarly, the next two groups of six columns describe the results of the second and the third division, respectively.

Overall, the experimental results show that `S2SLin` is the one (and only one) which could produce all correct results. Especially, it took a short time for the experiments

(8.38 seconds compared to 15.91 seconds of `Spen`, 324 minutes of `Songbird`, 635 minutes of `Harrsh`, 739 minutes of `SLS` and 2120 minutes of `CyclistSL`). While `SLS` returned 14 false negatives, `Spen` reported 20 false positives. `CyclistSL`, `Songbird` and `Harrsh` did not produce any wrong result. In total of 569 tests, while `CyclistSL` could manage 85 tests (15%), `Harrsh` could handle 215 tests (38%) and `Songbird` could decide 235 tests (41.3%). In total of 223 valid tests, while `CyclistSL` could manage 85 problems (38%), `Songbird` could decide 222 problems (99.5%).

In particular, the first division `qf_shls_entl` includes 122 invalid problems and 174 valid problems. For correct results, `Spen` returned all correct, `Songbird` 186, `Harrsh` 155, and `CyclistSL` 58. If we set the timeout to 2400 seconds, both `Songbird` and `Harrsh` produced all correct outcomes. The second division `qf_shlid_entl` includes 24 invalid problems and 36 valid problems. While `Songbird` produced 37 problems correctly, `CyclistSL` produced 24 correct results. `Spen` reported 27 correct results and 13 false positives (`sk12-vc{01 - 04}` `sk13-vc01`, `sk13-vc{03 - 10}`). The last division `qf_shlid2_entl` includes 14 invalid test problems and 13 valid test problems. While `Songbird` decided only 12 problems correctly, `CyclistSL` produced 3 correct outcomes. `Spen` reported 10 correct results. However, it produced 7 false positives (`1s-mul-vc{01 - 03}`, `1s-mul-vc05`, `n11-mul-vc{01 - 03}`).

7 Related Work

The closest works to `S2SLin` are the cyclic proof system presented by Brotherston [4,5,6,40] and two procedures focusing on inductive entailments [11,38]. Our work is based on the principles of the Brotherston cyclic proof system. In contrast to these systems, soundness of `S2SLin` is local and the proof is always linear. Our proposal also relates to those works that use lemmas as consequences of induction reasoning [3,16,25,29].

`Smallfoot` [3] proposed a decision procedure for a fragment with linked lists and trees (and without arithmetic). To handle inductive entailments, this system made use of a compositional rule as consequences of induction reasoning. This technique was further explored by the authors in [30]. The proposed proof system is designed in the same principle with `Smallfoot`. The main difference is that the compositional rule is replaced by rule `LInD` and the back-link construction. In doing so, our system could support induction reasoning over a much more expressive fragment of inductive predicates, i.e., mutually inductive predicates. The recent work presented in [40] shows the completeness of cyclic proof system. Its main contribution is the introduction of rule `*` for those entailments with disjunction in the RHS obtained from predicate unfolding. In contrast, we present normalization so as to soundly and completely avoid disjunction in the RHS while unfolding. Nevertheless, our decidable fragment `SHLIDe` is complement to the one introduced in [40]. Moreover, due to the empty heap in the base cases, the matching rule in [40] is unable to be applied into the predicates in `SHLIDe`.

In another direction, [29] generalize the cuts in an entailment with arbitrary inductive predicates through a manual lemma mechanism. Its induction principle is based on the cyclic proofs [4] and the soundness follows the substitution law [34]. Works in [16,24,25,39] automatically generate lemmas for some classes of inductive predicates. [24] generated lemmas to normalize (such as split, equate) the shapes of synthesized

data structures. Authors in [16] proposed to generate several sets of lemmas for not only compositional predicates but also different predicates (e.g., completion lemmas, stronger lemmas and static-parameter contraction lemmas). While the approach presented in [16] requires some additionally user-defined conditions over different predicates in the synthesized lemmas, $S2S_{Lin}$ works without these condition and thus might be more expressive. To prove an entailment, SLS [39] aims to infer general lemmas, starting from some templates, through two phases: one for LHS and another for RHS. Similarly, S2ENT [25] solves a more generic problem, the frame inference, using cyclic proofs and lemma synthesis. It first infers shape-based residual frame in the LHS and then synthesizes the pure constraints over the two sides. It would be a future work to integrate the pure constraint synthesis into $S2S_{Lin}$ to support non-local pure properties.

Our work relates to those works that reduce the entailment problem in separation logic into a well-studied problem in other domains. For instance, the problem with (possibly-cyclic) singly-linked lists and their invariants is reduced to the problem of inclusion checking in a graph theory [9,12,17]. The authors in [18] reduced the entailment problem to satisfiability problem in second-order monadic logic. This reduction could handle the most expressive fragment of spatial-based predicates, called bounded tree width. Recently, the work presented in [23] show a model-based decision procedure for the bounded tree width fragment. However, it is unclear how these works could support arithmetic constraints like our procedure. Besides, while works in [14,15,19] reduced the entailment problem in separation logic with inductive predicates to the inclusion checking problem of tree automata, [21] presented an idea in reducing the entailment problem into the inclusion checking problem of heap automata. Moreover, while the procedure in [14,15] supported well compositional (singly- and doubly-linked) predicates, the procedure in [19] could handle predicates satisfying local properties (e.g., trees with parent pointers). Our decidable fragment subsumes the one described in [3,14,15] but is incompatible to the ones presented in [9,17,18,19]. Works in [28] and [31,32] reduced the entailment problem in separation logic into the satisfiability problem in SMT. GRASShoper [31,32] is decision procedure in a fragment of multi-sorted first-order logic with reachability and trees. While GRASShoper could handle transitive closure pure properties, $S2S_{Lin}$ is able to support local ones. Unlike GRASShoper which reduces the entailment problem into SMT problems, $S2S_{Lin}$ reduces an entailment into admissible entailments as well as detects repetitions via cyclic proofs.

8 Conclusion

We have presented a novel decision procedure for the quantifier-free entailment problem in separation logic combining with inductive definitions of linear predicates and arithmetic properties. Our proposal is the first complete cyclic proof system for the problem in separation logic with arithmetic. We have implemented the proposal in $S2S_{Lin}$ and evaluated it over a set of non-trivial entailments taken from the competition for separation-logic-based solvers SL-COMP 2019. The experimental results show that our proposal is both effective and efficient when compared against the state-of-the-art solvers. It is promising for the modular verification of heap-manipulating programs.

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$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{RInd} \frac{\sigma = \circ \{ \bar{v}_i / \bar{p}_i \mid \bar{p}_i \in \bar{w} \wedge \bar{p}_i \neq \mathbf{null} \}}{x \mapsto c(\bar{v}) * \kappa_1 \wedge \pi_1 \wedge x \neq F \vdash (\exists (\bar{w} \setminus \bar{p}). x \mapsto c(\bar{p}) * \kappa' * \mathbf{P}(w, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg) \wedge \pi_0) \sigma * \kappa_2 \wedge \pi_2} \dagger \\
\text{LInd} \frac{(\exists (\bar{w} \setminus \bar{p}). x \mapsto c(\bar{p}) * \kappa' * \mathbf{P}(w, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg)^{k+1} \wedge \pi_0) * \kappa_1 \wedge \pi_1 \wedge x \neq F_3 \vdash \mathbf{Q}(x, F_3, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa_2 \wedge \pi_2}{\mathbf{P}(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)^k * \kappa_1 \wedge \pi_1 \wedge x \neq F_3 \vdash \mathbf{Q}(x, F_3, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa_2 \wedge \pi_2} \text{P}(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg) \notin \kappa_2
\end{array}$$

Fig. 6: Reduction Rules where $\dagger: x \mapsto c(\bar{v}) \notin \kappa_2$

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A Reduction Rules for Compositional Predicates in General Form

In Figure 6, we present rules RInd1 and LInd for the following definitions of compositional predicates:

$$\mathbf{P}(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg) \equiv \mathbf{emp} \wedge x = F \wedge sc = tg \vee \exists \bar{w}. x \mapsto c(\bar{p}) * \kappa' * \mathbf{P}(w, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg) \wedge \pi_0;$$

where \bar{w} are fresh variables.

To define SHLIDe base in a general form, we further assume every heap cells $c_i \in \mathit{Node}$ used in definitions of compositional predicates $\mathbf{P}(r, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)$ are defined in the form of `data c_i { c_i next; c_{i_1} down1; ...; c_{i_j} downj; τ_u udata; τ_s scdata }` where $c_{i_1}, \dots, c_{i_j} \in \mathit{Node}$, `down1`, ..., `downj` fields are for the nested structures in the matrix heaps, `udata` field is for the transitivity data, and `scdata` field are for ordering data. Then, SHLIDe base of an occurrence of the compositional predicates is defined as:

$$\overline{\mathbf{P}(E, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} E \mapsto c(F, \bar{d}, tg, u) [\bar{v} / \bar{d}] \wedge \pi_0 [tg / scd] * \kappa' ([\bar{v} / \bar{d}] \circ [tg / scd])$$

B Proof of Corollary 1

Proof. We need to show that the premises in rule RInd and rule LInd are quantifier-free. The condition C1 in section 2.1 ensures that $\bar{w} \subseteq \bar{p}$. Hence, $\bar{w} \setminus \bar{p} \equiv \emptyset$. Thus, the RHS of the premise in RInd and the LHS of the premise in LU are quantifier-free.

Fig. 7: An Example of Non-Disjoint Back-Links.

C Proof of Soundness

We show the correctness of the soundness of the proof system.

C.1 Local Soundness: Lemma 1

The proof of the local soundness could be found in the existing works e.g., [20,35,2,3,5,10]. For a self-content paper, we briefly describe the proofs of each rule.

The rule `SUBST` is the standard substitution law. The soundness of rules exclude-the-middle `EXM`, `=L`, `=R`, `HYPOTHESIS`, `RInd`, and `LInd` is straightforward.

The soundness of rule `LBase` is based on the fact that given a compositional predicate $P(E, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)$ where F is a dangling pointer, then $P(E, E, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)$ implies the base rule with `emp` heap predicate. Finally, the soundness of rule `≠null` is based on the semantics of heap locations where `null` \notin `Loc`. The soundness of rule `≠*` is based on the semantics of the separating conjunction `*`.

C.2 Global Soundness: Lemma 2

As our system always generates back-links with progressing points (via rule `LInd`), we now show that all cycles are pairwise disjoint (such that in the path between a companion and a bud of every back-link, no rule can ever “delete” an inductive predicate formula on which the soundness relies). We prove by contradiction.

In intuition, the soundness relies on a pair of inductive predicates in a sub-term relationship. Given an inductive predicate $P(E, F, \bar{B}, \bar{v})$ only rule `EXM` is able to generate the constraint $E=F$ such that $P(E, F, \bar{B}, \bar{v})$ can be transformed into $P(F, F, \bar{B}, \bar{v}')$ via rule `SUBST` and finally eliminated by rule `LBase`. We now show that every companion node of a back-link involving a bud that is in the branch $E \neq F$ of rule `EXM` is below the node including the applications of rule `EXM`.

Assume that our system generates back-links with non-disjoint cycles. Two cycles are non-disjoint only when their both companion nodes are above at least one branch (applications of rule EXM). The non-disjoint cycles is similar to the one as shown in the proof tree in Fig. 7 where there is no branch in the path between Δ_2 and Δ_3 . (The proof for the case where Δ_5 is linked with Δ_2 and Δ_6 is linked with Δ_3 is similar. We discuss this proof below.)

We prove the contradiction by case analysis on the pair of variables E_1 and E_2 applied with rule EXM at node Δ_4 . As EXM is applied to introduce $G(op(E))$ for every $op(E)$ in the LHS of entailments. We proceed case analysis on $op(E)$.

1. Case 1. $op(E) \equiv E \mapsto _$ and EXM at node Δ_4 does case split $E = \text{null}$ and $E \neq \text{null}$ to obtain two children. Assume that the left child (on the path from Δ_4 to Δ_5) is $\Delta_4 \wedge E = \text{null}$. After substitution, LHS of this node is reduced to $\Delta'_4 * \text{null} \mapsto _$ which is equivalent to false . Thus, the back-link from Δ_5 to Δ_3 could not established.
2. Case 2. $op(E) \equiv P(E, F, \bar{B}, \bar{v})$ and EXM at node Δ_4 does case split $E = F$ and $E \neq F$ to obtain two children. Assume that the left child (on the path from Δ_4 to Δ_5) is $\Delta_4 \wedge E = F$. After substitution, LHS of this node is reduced to $\Delta'_4 * P(F, F, \bar{B}, \bar{v}')$. In turn, this entailment is applied with normalization rule LBase to eliminate $P(F, F, \bar{B}, \bar{v}')$. Next, we consider two sub-cases of the inductive predicate in any application of rule LInd applied into a node between Δ_3 and Δ_5 .
 - (a) the predicate applied is $P(E', F, \bar{B}, \bar{v})$. We note that in the recursive rule of definitions of compositional predicates

$$\exists X, sc', d_1, d_2. x \mapsto c(X, d_1, d_2, u, sc) * Q_1(d_1, B) * Q_2(d_2, X) * P(X, F, \bar{B}, u, sc', tg) \wedge \pi_0$$

all nested predicates Q_1, Q_2 are syntactically different to P . Δ_5 is missing one occurrence of predicate P . Hence, it could not be linked back to Δ_3 .

- (b) the predicate applied is $Q(E', F', F, \bar{v}')$ such that $P(U, F, \bar{B}, u', sc', tg')$ is a nested predicate in the definition of Q . However, u', tg' are fresh variables and in any back-links they are never substituted to become u and tg , respectively. Hence, Δ_5 could not be linked back to Δ_3 .
3. Case 3. $op(E) \equiv \text{tree}(E, \bar{B}, \bar{v})$ and EXM at node Δ_4 does case split $E = \text{null}$ and $E \neq \text{null}$ to obtain two children. As LInd only applies for compositional predicates, $\text{tree}(E, \bar{B}, \bar{v})$ could not be a fresh formula. It has been normalised in Δ_3 already. This case could not be occurred.

The proof for the case where Δ_5 is linked with Δ_2 and Δ_6 is linked with Δ_3 is similar. The main difference is that we need to show that predicate $P(E, F, \bar{B}, \bar{v})$ is a sub-formula of Δ_2 in the proof of **Case 2** like above. That means $P(E, F, \bar{B}, \bar{v})$ has not been eliminated by rule EXM in the path between Δ_2 Δ_3 . This is straightforward as no branch exists in the path between Δ_2 and Δ_3 .

D Proofs of Termination

D.1 Proof of Lemma 3

Proof. Termination of our system is based on the size of an entailment which is defined as:

Definition 6 (Size) The size of an entailment $\mathfrak{e}:\kappa_a \wedge \phi_a \wedge a_a \vdash \kappa_c \wedge \phi_c \wedge a_c$ is a triple of:

1. $N_p - n_p$ where N_p is the maximal number of both points-to predicates and occurrences of inductive predicates that the RHS of any entailments derived (by ω -ENT) from \mathfrak{e} may contain, and n_p is the total number of both points-to predicates and occurrences of inductive predicates in κ_c .
2. $N_e - n_e$ where N_e is the maximal number of both disequalities and non-trivial equalities that the LHS of any entailments derived (by ω -ENT) from \mathfrak{e} may contain, and n_e is the number of both disequalities and non-trivial equalities in ϕ_a .
3. the sum of the length of $\kappa_a \wedge \phi_a \wedge a_a \vdash \kappa_c \wedge \phi_c \wedge a_c$, where length is defined in the obvious way taking all simple formulas to have length 1.

If N_p and N_e are bounded, applying any rules except LInd makes progress since the size of each premise of any rule application is lexicographically less than the size of the conclusion. N_p relies on the number of applications of rule LInd. N_e depends on the number applications of rule EXM. In turn, the application of EXM relies on the number of spatial variables. Thus, N_e also relies on the number applications of rule LInd. To show the termination, we show that the number applications of rule LInd is bounded. In consequence, this bound is achieved if the number of applications of $*$ is finite. As the number of inductive symbols as their arities are finite, rule $*$ indeed generates a finite number of equivalent classes of entailments in which two entailments in the same class are equivalent after some substitution. Thus, all entailments in the same class are linked back together through a finite number of steps.

D.2 Proof of Lemma 4

Suppose we have an entailment $P(E, F, \bar{B}, \bar{v})^k * \kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa' \wedge \pi'$. If $\pi \not\models \pi'$ then exhaustively applying rule EXM our system decides it as `invalid` through the base cases like $E = F$.

If $\pi \models \pi'$, then our system applies rule HYP0 to obtain $P(E, F, \bar{B}, \bar{v})^k * \kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa'$. Hence, in the following proof, we only consider the later form of the entailment in conclusion of rule LInd.

Without loss of generality, we assume \mathcal{P} includes 4 predicates definitions: P_1, P_2, Q_1 and Q_2 where $P_1 \prec_{\mathcal{P}} P_2$ (that is the recursive branch of predicate definition P_2 contains one and only one occurrence of predicate P_1 and P_1 is self-recursive), $Q_1 \prec_{\mathcal{P}} Q_2$ (that is the recursive branch of predicate definition Q_2 contains one and only one occurrence of predicate Q_1 and Q_1 is self-recursive), $P_1 \not\prec_{\mathcal{P}} Q_1, P_1 \not\prec_{\mathcal{P}} Q_2, P_2 \not\prec_{\mathcal{P}} Q_1,$ and $P_2 \not\prec_{\mathcal{P}} Q_2$. For instance, the definitions of these predicates could be as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{pred } P_1(r, F, u) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \\
&\quad \vee \exists X, sc'. r \mapsto c_1(X, -, u, -, -) * P_1(X, F, u) \wedge r \neq F \wedge a_1 \\
\text{pred } P_2(r, F, B_1, u, sc, tg) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \wedge sc = tg \\
&\quad \vee \exists X, d, u', sc'. r \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u') * P_2(X, F, B_1, u, sc', tg) \wedge r \neq F \wedge a_2 \\
\text{pred } Q_1(r, F, u) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \\
&\quad \vee \exists X, sc'. r \mapsto c_2(X, -, u, -, -) * Q_1(X, F, u) \wedge r \neq F \wedge a_3 \\
\text{pred } Q_2(r, F, B_1, u, sc, tg) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \wedge sc = tg \\
&\quad \vee \exists X, d, u', sc'. r \mapsto c_2(X, d, u, u', sc') * Q_1(d, B, u') * Q_2(X, F, B_1, u, sc', tg) \wedge r \neq F \wedge a_4
\end{aligned}$$

We notice that in the definitions of P_2 and Q_2 , we assume that in the recursive rule sc' is a variable of a field of the root points-to predicate. In general, it may be a parameter of P_2 and Q_2 as well.

If the input entailment is in NF and of the form: $P(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)^0 * \Delta \vdash \Delta'$ and there does not exist an occurrence of inductive predicate $Q(x, F_2, \bar{B}, \dots) \in \Delta'$ then this entailment satisfy the case 2c in Sect. 4.1 and is classified as `invalid` immediately. Thus, the Lemma holds. In the rest, to prove this Lemma, we only need to consider the application of rule `LInd` where the entailment is in NF and of the form in the conclusion of `LInd` as:

$$e_0: P(x, F, B, u, sc, tg)^0 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \vdash Q(x, F_2, B, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa'$$

Furthermore, it is safe to assume that $P(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)^0$ is the only one with the smallest unfolding number (i.e., 0) in the LHS of e_0 could be applied with rule `LInd`. We prove it by the structural induction on the number of occurrences of inductive predicates in the LHS of the input entailment. We do case splits.

D.3 Case 1: P and Q have the same definition.

We consider two cases where the definition contains nested structures or not.

Case 1.1 For the simplest scenario, we assume both definitions of P and Q are self-recursive and do not contain nested structures i.e., $P \equiv Q \equiv P_1$. Then, e_0 becomes:

$$e_{1_1}: P_1(x, F, u)^0 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \vdash P_1(x, F_2, u) * \kappa'$$

After applied with rule `LInd`, our system generates a premise as follows.

$$e_{1_{1_1}}: x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, sc', uprm) * P_1(X, F, u)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{1_1} \vdash P_1(x, F_2, u) * \kappa'$$

where X, d, sc' and $uprm$ are two fresh variables and a_{1_1} is the arithmetical constraint obtained by substituting actual/formal parameters into the constraint a_1 of the recursive rule of the definition of P_1 . Next, entailment $e_{1_{1_1}}$ is normalized by applying rule `≠null` to obtain:

$$e_{1_{1_1}}: x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, sc', uprm) * P_1(X, F, u)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{1_1} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \vdash P_1(x, F_2, u) * \kappa'$$

Now, $e_{1_{1_2}}$ is applied with rule `RInd1` to obtain:

$$e_{1_{1_3}}: x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, sc', uprm) * P_1(X, F, u)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{1_1} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, sc', uprm) * P_1(x, F_2, u) * \kappa' \wedge a_{1_1}$$

We note that for completeness applications of rule `*` are always performed after all other rules. As so, next, `HYP0` is applied to eliminate the arithmetical constraint in the RHS to obtain:

$$e_{1_{1_4}}: x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, sc', uprm) * P_1(X, F, u)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{1_1} \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, sc', uprm) * P_1(x, F_2, u) * \kappa'$$

Our system now applies rules EXM and $\neq*$ to normalize the LHS where application of the latter rule generates two premises.

$$\begin{aligned} e_{1_{15}} &: x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, sc', uprm) * P_1(X, F, u)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{1_1} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge X = F \\ &\quad \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, sc', uprm) * P_1(x, F_2, u) * \kappa' \\ e_{1_{16}} &: x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, sc', uprm) * P_1(X, F, u)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{1_1} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge X \neq F \\ &\quad \wedge x \neq X \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, sc', uprm) * P_1(x, F_2, u) * \kappa' \end{aligned}$$

1. For the premise $e_{1_{15}}$, our system applies rules SUBST and $L =$ to eliminate $X = F$ and obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} e_{1_{15_1}} &: x \mapsto c_1(F, d, u, sc', uprm) * P_1(F, F, u)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{1_1} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \\ &\quad \vdash x \mapsto c_1(F, d, u, sc', uprm) * P_1(x, F_2, u) * \kappa' \end{aligned}$$

Next, rule LBase1 is applied to discard the inductive predicate in the LHS and obtain the following premise:

$$\begin{aligned} e_{1_{15_2}} &: x \mapsto c_1(F, d, u, sc', uprm) * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{1_1} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \\ &\quad \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, sc', uprm) * P_1(x, F_2, u) * \kappa' \end{aligned}$$

As the number of inductive predicates in the LHS of $e_{1_{15_2}}$ is reduced, by induction, this Lemma holds.

2. For the premise $e_{1_{16}}$, our system links it back to e_{1_1} as follows. First, it weakens (a.k.a discards) two matched points-to predicates in the two sides and the following pure constraints in LHS: $x \neq F$, a_{1_1} , $x \neq \text{null}$, and $x \neq X$. After that, it substitutes the remaining entailment with $\sigma = \{x/X\}$ to obtain the identical entailment with e_{1_1} . We notice that as X is a fresh variable, it does not appear in $\kappa \wedge \pi$ and κ' . Then, the Lemma holds for this case.

Case 1.2 For a more general case, we assume $P \equiv Q \equiv P_2$. Then, e_0 becomes:

$$e_{1_2} : P_2(x, F, B, u, sc, tg)^0 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \vdash P_2(x, F_2, B, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa'$$

The first four steps are similar to **Case 1.1**. After applied with rule LInd, our system generates a premise as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} e_{1_{2_1}} &: x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u')^1 * P_2(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{2_1} \\ &\quad \vdash P_2(x, F_2, B, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa' \end{aligned}$$

where a_{2_1} is obtained by substituting actual/formal paramters into the arithmetical constraint a_2 of the recursive rule of the definition of P_2 . Next, this entailment is normalized by applying rule $\neq \text{null}$ to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} e_{1_{2_2}} &: x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u')^1 * P_2(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{2_1} \\ &\quad \wedge x \neq \text{null} \vdash P_2(x, F_2, B, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa' \end{aligned}$$

Next, $e_{1_{2_2}}$ is applied with rule RInd1 to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} e_{1_{2_3}} &: x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u')^1 * P_2(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{2_1} \\ &\quad \wedge x \neq \text{null} \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u')^0 * P_2(X, F_2, B, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa' \wedge a_{2_1} \end{aligned}$$

We note that rule $*$ is always applied after all other rules. As so, next, HYPOTHESIS is applied to eliminate the arithmetical constraint in the RHS to obtain:

$$e_{124} : x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u')^1 * P_2(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{21} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u')^0 * P_2(X, F_2, B, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa'$$

Our system now applies rules EXM and $\neq*$ to normalize the LHS. Particularly, applying rule EXM for d and B generates two premises:

$$e_{125} : x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u')^1 * P_2(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{21} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge d = B \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u')^0 * P_2(X, F_2, B, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa'$$

$$e_{126} : x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u')^1 * P_2(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{21} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge d \neq B \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u')^0 * P_2(X, F_2, B, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa'$$

1. For the first premise e_{125} , our system first applies rules SUBST to obtain and $L =$:

$$e_{125_1} : x \mapsto c_1(X, B, u, u', sc') * P_1(B, B, u')^1 * P_2(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{21} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, B, u, u', sc') * P_1(B, B, u')^0 * P_2(X, F_2, B, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa'$$

After that, it applies rules LBase and RBase to eliminate inductive predicates P_1 in the LHS and RHS, respectively. Afterward, the premise is obtained as:

$$e_{125_3} : x \mapsto c_1(X, B, u, u', sc') * P_2(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{21} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, B, u, u', sc') * P_2(X, F_2, B, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa'$$

Now, it generates a back-link between e_{125_3} and e_{12} . Hence, the Lemma holds.

2. For the second premise e_{126} , the system applies rule $\neq*$ and then rule EXM to obtain two following premises:

$$e_{127} : x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u')^1 * P_2(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{21} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge d \neq B \wedge x \neq d \wedge X = F \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u') * P_2(X, F_2, B, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa'$$

$$e_{128} : x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u')^1 * P_2(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{21} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge d \neq B \wedge x \neq d \wedge X \neq F \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u') * P_2(X, F_2, B, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa'$$

- (a) For the premise e_{127} , our system applies rules SUBST and $L =$ first and then rule LBase to eliminate inductive predicates P_2 in the LHS. Afterward, the premise is obtained as:

$$e_{127_3} : x \mapsto c_1(F, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u')^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{21} \wedge x \neq \text{null} \wedge d \neq B \wedge x \neq d \vdash x \mapsto c_1(F, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u') * P_2(F, F_2, B, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa'$$

Similarly to **Case 1.1**, the Lemma holds for e_{127_3} .

- (b) For the premise e_{128} , our system links it back to e_{12} . Hence, the Lemma holds.

D.4 Case 2: P and Q have different definitions and they are syntactically dependent.

We consider two sub-cases. In the first case, we assume $P \prec_{\mathcal{P}} Q$. In the second case, we assume $Q \prec_{\mathcal{P}} P$.

Case 2.1: $P \prec_{\mathcal{P}} Q$ For a general case, we assume $P \equiv P'_1$ and $Q \equiv P'_2$ where P'_1 is defined similarly to P_1 except it contains an additional local property (Otherwise, the proof for $P \equiv P_1$ and $Q \equiv P_2$ is quite trivial.).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pred } P'_1(r, F, u, sc, tg) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \wedge sc = tg \\ &\vee \exists X, sc'. r \rightarrow c_1(X, -, u, -, sc') * P'_1(X, F, u, sc', tg) \wedge r \neq F \wedge a_1 \\ \text{pred } P'_2(r, F, B_1, u, sc, tg) &\equiv \text{emp} \wedge r = F \wedge sc = tg \\ &\vee \exists X, d, u', sc'. r \rightarrow c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P'_1(d, B, u', sc, tg) * P'_2(X, F, B_1, u, sc', tg) \wedge r \neq F \wedge a_2 \end{aligned}$$

Then, e_0 becomes:

$$e_{2_1}: P'_1(x, F, B, u, sc, tg)^0 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \vdash P'_2(x, F_2, B, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa'$$

After applying three rules **LInd**, $\neq \text{null}$ and **RInd** in sequence (and similarly to **Case 1.1** and **Case 1.2** above), our system generates the following premise.

$$\begin{aligned} e_{2_{1_3}}: x \rightarrow c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P'_1(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{1_1} \\ \vdash x \rightarrow c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P'_1(d, B, u', sc, tg) * P_2(X, F_2, B, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa' \wedge a_{2_1} \end{aligned}$$

where X, d, sc' and u' are two fresh variables. Our system applies rule **EXM** for d and B to generate the following two premises.

$$\begin{aligned} e_{2_{1_4}}: x \rightarrow c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P'_1(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge d = B \wedge a_{1_1} \\ \vdash x \rightarrow c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P'_1(d, B, u', sc, tg) * P_2(X, F_2, B, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa' \wedge a_{2_1} \\ e_{2_{1_5}}: x \rightarrow c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P'_1(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge d \neq B \wedge a_{1_1} \\ \vdash x \rightarrow c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P'_1(d, B, u', sc, tg) * P_2(X, F_2, B, u, sc', tg_2) * \kappa' \wedge a_{2_1} \end{aligned}$$

As d is a fresh variable, the predicate $P'_1(d, B, u', sc, tg)$ does not appear in the LHS of $e_{2_{1_5}}$. Hence, $e_{2_{1_5}}$ is classified as **invalid** and ω -ENT returns **invalid**. Hence, the Lemma holds.

Case 2.2: $Q \prec_{\mathcal{P}} P$ For a general case, we assume $P \equiv P_2$ and $Q \equiv P_1$. Then, e_0 becomes:

$$e_{2_2}: P_2(x, F, B, u, sc, tg)^0 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \vdash P_1(x, F_2, B, u) * \kappa'$$

The proof for this case is similar to **Case 2.1**. After applying three rules **LInd**, $\neq \text{null}$ and **RInd** in sequence, our system generates the following premise.

$$\begin{aligned} e_{2_{2_3}}: x \rightarrow c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u') * P_2(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^0 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{2_1} \\ \vdash x \rightarrow c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(X, F_2, B, u) * \kappa' \wedge a_{1_1} \end{aligned}$$

where X, d, sc' and u' are two fresh variables. Our system applies rule `EXM` for d and B to generate the following two premises.

$$\begin{aligned} e_{224} &: x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u') * P_2(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^0 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{21} \wedge d = B \\ &\quad \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(X, F_2, B, u) * \kappa' \wedge a_{11} \\ e_{225} &: x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(d, B, u') * P_2(X, F, B, u, sc', tg)^0 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \wedge a_{21} \wedge d \neq B \\ &\quad \vdash x \mapsto c_1(X, d, u, u', sc') * P_1(X, F_2, B, u) * \kappa' \wedge a_{11} \end{aligned}$$

As d is a fresh variable, the predicate $P_1(d, B, u')$ does not appear in the RHS of e_{225} . Hence, e_{225} is classified as `invalid` and ω -ENT returns `invalid`. Hence, the Lemma holds.

D.5 Case 3: P and Q have different definitions and they are syntactically independent.

We consider three sub-cases based on the positions of inductive predicates in the dependency hierarchies. In the first case, we assume P is “bigger” than Q. In the second case, we assume P is “smaller” than Q. And in the last case, we assume P is “equal” to Q.

Case 3.1: We assume $P \equiv P_2$ and $Q \equiv Q_1$. Then, e_0 becomes:

$$e_{31} : P_2(x, F, B, u, sc, tg)^0 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \vdash Q_1(x, F_2, B, u) * \kappa'$$

If $c_1 \neq c_2$, `is_closed` returns `invalid` (Case 2d in Sect. 4.1). Otherwise, the proof for this case is similar to **Case 2.2**.

Case 3.2: We assume $P \equiv P'_1$ and $Q \equiv Q_2$. Then, e_0 becomes:

$$e_{32} : P'_1(x, F, B, u, sc, tg)^0 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \vdash Q_2(x, F_2, B, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa'$$

If $c_1 \neq c_2$, the proof is straightforward. Otherwise, the proof for this case is similar to **Case 2.1**.

Case 3.3: We assume $P \equiv P_1$ and $Q \equiv Q_1$. Then, e_0 becomes:

$$e_{33} : P_2(x, F, B, u)^0 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \vdash Q_2(x, F_2, B, u) * \kappa'$$

If $c_1 \neq c_2$, the proof is straightforward. Otherwise, the proof for this case is similar to **Case 1.1**.

Case 3.4: We assume $P \equiv P_2$ and $Q \equiv Q_2$. Then, e_0 becomes:

$$e_{34} : P_2(x, F, B, u, sc, tg)^0 * \kappa \wedge \pi \wedge x \neq F \wedge x \neq F_2 \vdash Q_2(x, F_2, B, u, sc, tg_2) * \kappa'$$

If $c_1 \neq c_2$, the proof is straightforward. Otherwise, the proof for this case is similar to **Case 1.2**.

□.

E Complexity Analysis - Proposition 1

The input entailment initially contains at most m variables and could be applied rule EXM at most $(m-1) + (m-2) + \dots + 1 = \mathcal{O}(m^2)$ times.

Each occurrence of inductive predicates in LHS of the input is applied with LInd at most one to generate at most M other nested occurrences of inductive predicates in the matrix heap (in the recursive rule). Each entailment derived contains at most $2m$ variables and could be applied rule EXM $\mathcal{O}((2m)^2)$ times.

In turn, each of these M predicates is applied with LInd at most one to generate at most M other nested occurrences of inductive predicates. This process is kept repeated until the LHS contains all predicates whose definitions are not nested. As the system of definitions does not allow mutual recursion, then this process is repeated at most n times. Hence, the number of inductive predicate occurrence is generated from each occurrence of inductive predicates in LHS of the input is $\mathcal{O}(M^{n-1})$. As the LHS of the input contains at most n occurrences of predicates, the number of predicate occurrences could be generated in the LHS is $\mathcal{O}(M^n)$. Each entailment derived contains at most $\mathcal{O}(n^2m)$ variables. Hence, this entailment could be applied rule EXM $\mathcal{O}((n^2m)^2)$ times.

The size of an entailment could be

$$\begin{aligned} & n(\mathcal{O}(m^2) + \mathcal{O}((2m)^2M) + \dots + \mathcal{O}((n^2m)^2M^n)) \\ &= n(\mathcal{O}((n^2m)^2(1 + M + M^2 + \dots + M^n))) \\ &= n(\mathcal{O}((n^2m)^2M^{n+1})) \\ &= \mathcal{O}(n^5m^2M^{n+1}) \end{aligned}$$

F Proof of Local Completeness - Lemma 6

The completeness of all rules except rule $*$ is straightforward. In the following, we prove the completeness of rule $*$. The proof is based on the following auxiliary Lemma.

Lemma 8. *If $\kappa \wedge \phi \wedge a$ is in NF and $x \neq E \notin \phi$, then $(\kappa \wedge \phi)[E/x] \wedge a$ is in NF.*

Proof. All but the fifth clause in the definition 3 are invariant under substitution. Moreover, $x \neq E \notin \phi$ exclude the violation of the fifth clause under substitution as well \square .

First, we provide proofs for pure part when heaps in both sides are identical and pure constraints in LHS does not imply pure constraints in RHS.

Proposition 3. *If $\kappa_m \wedge \phi \wedge a \vdash \kappa_m \wedge \phi' \wedge a'$ is in NF and $e': \text{emp} \wedge \phi \wedge a \vdash \text{emp} \wedge \phi' \wedge a'$ is not derivable, then $\kappa_m \wedge \phi \wedge a \vdash \kappa_m \wedge \phi' \wedge a'$ is invalid.*

Proof. We show that there is a model of the LHS such that either $\neg\phi'$ or $\neg a'$ holds. We proceed cases for each predicate in the RHS.

1. Case $\phi' \equiv E_1 = E_2$. As the LHS is in NF, any bad model of $\overline{\kappa_m} \wedge \phi \wedge a$ implies that $E_1 \neq E_2$. In other words, $\overline{\kappa_m} \wedge \phi \wedge a$ implies that $\neg E_1 = E_2$.

2. Case $\phi' \equiv E_1 \neq E_2$. As e' is not derivable, then the side condition of rule HYPOTHESIS does not hold. This means $E_1 \neq E_2 \notin \phi$.

We note that if $\kappa_m \wedge \phi \wedge a$ is in NF and $E_1 \neq E_2 \notin \phi$, then $(\kappa_m \wedge \phi \wedge a)[E_1/E_2]$ is also in NF (assuming that E_1 is a variable - Lemma 8). Then suppose s, h be a bad model of $(\overline{\kappa_m} \wedge \phi \wedge a)[E_1/E_2]$, then $s[E_1 \mapsto s(E_2)], h$ is a model of $(\overline{\kappa_m} \wedge \phi \wedge a)$. $s[E_1 \mapsto s(E_2)], h$ implies that $\neg E_1 \neq E_2$. Therefore, $(\overline{\kappa_m} \wedge \phi \wedge a)$ does not imply $E_1 \neq E_2$. Neither is $(\kappa_m \wedge \phi \wedge a)$.

3. Case $\phi' \equiv \text{true}$. As e' is not derivable, then the side condition of rule HYPOTHESIS does not hold. This means $a \not\models a'$. Hence, any model of a implies $\neg a'$.

Therefore, any bad model of $\overline{\kappa_m} \wedge \phi \wedge a$ is a counter-model. \square

Secondly, we prove the completeness of rule $*$ when the LHS of the conclusion in NF is a base formula.

$$* \frac{\kappa_1 \vdash \kappa_2 \quad \kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa'}{\kappa_1 * \kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa_2 * \kappa'}$$

Proof. We prove that if invalidity of the rule's premises implies invalidity of the rule's conclusion. For any s, h , we have $s, h \models x_1 \mapsto c_1(\bar{v}_1) * \dots * x_n \mapsto c_n(\bar{v}_n) \wedge \pi$, then $\text{dom}(h) = \{s(x_1), \dots, s(x_n)\}$. We proceed by cases.

1. Case 1: $\kappa_2 \equiv x_i \mapsto c_i(\bar{v}_i)$. As $\kappa_1 \not\models \kappa_2$, for all $j \in \{1 \dots n\}$, $s, \{s(x_j)\} \not\models x_i \mapsto c_i(\bar{v}_i)$, then $x_i \neq x_j$ for all $j \in \{1 \dots n\}$. Hence $s, h \not\models \kappa_2 * \kappa'$.
2. Case 2: $\kappa_2 \equiv \text{P}(r, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)$. We notice that $r \equiv x_j, j \in \{1 \dots n\}$. Otherwise, procedure *is_closed* has returned *invalid* already. Secondly, $r \neq F \in \pi$. Otherwise, ω -ENT is stuck (it could not apply rule RInd). Thus, procedure *is_closed* has also returned *invalid* already. There are two ways $\kappa_1 \not\models \kappa_2$.
 - First, κ_1 does not contain a set of points-to predicates starting from r and ending at $\{F\} \cup \bar{B}$. By semantics of the compositional predicate, $s, h \not\models \kappa_2 * \kappa'$.
 - Secondly, κ_1 is not in the form of SHLIDe Base (Definition 4). It is straightforward $s, h \not\models \kappa_2 * \kappa'$.

We notice that, as the LHS is in NF, there is one and only one set of points-to predicates κ_2 such that $\kappa_1 \models \kappa_2$.

\square

G Proof of Global Completeness - Proposition 2

We prove the correctness of Proposition 2 through two steps:

1. proofs for the case where LHS is a base formula. Those entailments are reduced without LInd.
2. proofs for the case where LHS is a general formula. Those entailments are reduced with LInd prior to applying other rules.

In the proofs, we make use of the following auxiliary Lemmas.

Lemma 9. *If $\overline{\kappa} \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa'_1 * \kappa'_2$ in NF is derivable, then there exist κ_1, κ_2 such that $\kappa \equiv \kappa_1 * \kappa_2$ and both $\overline{\kappa_1} \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa'_1$ and $\overline{\kappa_2} \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa'_2$ are derivable.*

Lemma 10. *If $\overline{\kappa}_1 * \overline{\kappa}_2 \wedge \pi$ is in NF and $\overline{\kappa}_1 \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa'_1$ is valid, then $\overline{\kappa}_1 * \overline{\kappa}_2 \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa'_1 * \kappa'_2$ is valid iff $\overline{\kappa}_2 \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa'_2$ is valid.*

Based on the fact that heaps of a normalized base formula is precise. The proof is straightforward based on the semantics of the separating conjunction $*$.

G.1 Base-Formula LHS

First, we show the correctness of case 2a) of procedure `is_closed` i.e., an entailment is stuck then it is invalid. After that, we show the invalidity is preserved through proof search.

As the LHS is a base formula, rule `LInd` (and rule `LBase`) is never be applied. We prove case 2a) by induction on the number of disequalities missing from the LHS and generated by rule `EXM`. First, we prove the case where the RHS is an occurrence of compositional predicate P assuming that the points-to predidcate in the definition of P is c .

Lemma 11. *If $e_0: x \mapsto c(F_2, \bar{p}, u) * \bar{\kappa} \wedge \phi \wedge a \vdash P(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)$ is in NF and is stuck, then it is invalid.*

Proof. Due to the stuckness, ω -ENT could not applies rule `RInd`. Hence, $x \neq F \notin \phi$. As the the entailment is in NF, $(x \mapsto c(F_2, \bar{p}, u) * \bar{\kappa} \wedge \phi)[F/x] \wedge a \vdash P(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)[F/x]$ is in NF (by Lemma 8). As all models satisfying the LHS $(x \mapsto c(F_2, \bar{p}, u) * \bar{\kappa} \wedge \phi)[F/x] \wedge a$ are non-empty heap and in NF, all models satisfying the RHS $P(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)[F/x] \equiv P(F, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)$ are empty heap, this entailment is invalid. As the substitution law is sound and complete [34], e_0 is invalid. \square .

Lemma 12. *If $e_0: \bar{\kappa} \wedge \phi \wedge a \vdash \kappa'$ is in NF and is stuck, then it is invalid.*

Proof. By induction on the number of disequalities missing from ϕ . We proceed by cases.

1. $\kappa' \equiv P(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg) * \kappa''$ assuming that the points-to predidcate in the definition of P is c .
 - (a) $op(x) \notin \bar{\kappa}$. This case is the case 2c) of procedure `is_closed`. The bad model of the LHS is the counter-model.
 - (b) $op(x) \in \bar{\kappa}$. ω -ENT reduces the entailments by first applying rule `EXM` prior to applying rule `LInd`. We are considering the case ω -ENT could not apply rule `LInd`. We proceed cases for the LHS.
 - i. $\kappa \equiv x \mapsto c(F_2, \bar{v}) * \bar{\kappa}_0$ and $x \neq F \notin \phi$.
If $e_1: x \mapsto c(F_2, \bar{v}) * \bar{\kappa}_0 \wedge \phi \wedge a \wedge \mathbf{x} \neq \mathbf{F} \vdash P(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg) * \kappa''$ is stuck, rule `LInd` could not be applied. Hence, $x \mapsto c(F_2, \bar{v}) \in \kappa''$. Therefore, there is no model that satisfies the RHS. This entailment e_1 is thus invalid. As rule `EXM` is complete (Lemma 6), e_0 is invalid.
If e_1 is derivable, following Lemma 9, there exist κ_1, κ_2 such that $\kappa_0 \equiv \kappa_1 * \kappa_2$ and both $e_2: x \mapsto c(F_2, \bar{v}) * \bar{\kappa}_1 \wedge \phi \wedge a \wedge \mathbf{x} \neq \mathbf{F} \vdash P(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)$ and $e_3: \bar{\kappa}_2 \wedge \phi \wedge a \wedge \mathbf{x} \neq \mathbf{F} \vdash \kappa''$ are derivable. We proceed two sub-cases:

- A. $e'_3: \bar{\kappa}_2 \wedge \phi \wedge a \vdash \kappa''$ is stuck. Hence either $op_1x \in \bar{\kappa}_2$ or $op_2(F) \in \bar{\kappa}_2$. This implies either $opx * op_1x$ in the LHS of e_0 or $opx * op_3F$ in the LHS of e_0 . As e_0 is in NF, either $x \neq x \in \phi$ or $x \neq F \in \phi$. Both can't happen as the first scenario contradicts with assumption that LHS is in LHS and the second one contradicts with assumption $x \neq F \notin \phi$.
- B. $e'_3: \bar{\kappa}_2 \wedge \phi \wedge a \vdash \kappa''$ is derivable. Hence, by soundness (Lemma 2), it is valid. (2a)
 - As e_0 is stuck and e'_3 is derivable, we deduce that $e'_2: x \mapsto c(F_2, \bar{v}) * \bar{\kappa}_1 \wedge \phi \wedge a \vdash P(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg)$ is stuck (Otherwise, e_0 is derivable as well, contradiction). By Lemma 11, e'_2 is invalid. (2b)
 - By (2a), (2b) and Lemma 10, e_0 is invalid.
- ii. $\kappa \equiv x \mapsto c'(F_2, \bar{v}) * \bar{\kappa}_0, x \neq F \in \phi$ and $c' \neq c$. The proof is similar to Case 2d of procedure `is_closed`. The bad model of the LHS is the counter-model.
- 2. $\kappa' \equiv x \mapsto c(\bar{v}) * \kappa''$. Straightforward.
- 3. $\kappa' \equiv \text{emp}$. Straightforward.

□.

Proposition 4. *If $\bar{\kappa} \wedge \phi \wedge a \vdash \kappa'$ is in NF and is not derivable, then it is invalid.*

Proof. In a incomplete proof, if a leaf node in NF is stuck then it is invalid (Lemma 12 and Lemma 3). The invalidity is preserved up to the root based on Lemma 6. □.

G.2 General LHS

By induction on the RHS. We proceed cases on the RHS. In the proofs, for convenient, we write $\kappa_a \wedge \pi_a \vdash_{\kappa} \kappa_c \wedge \pi_c$ as a shorthand of $\kappa_a * \kappa \wedge \pi_a \vdash \kappa_c * \kappa \wedge \pi_c$ and no any matching heaps between κ_a and κ_c could be found through the application of rule $*$.

Lemma 13. *If $e: \kappa \wedge \pi \vdash_{\kappa_m} \kappa'$ in NF where $e_0: \kappa \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa'$ is stuck, then e_0 is invalid.*

Proof. We first show e_0 is invalid. After that by using Lemma 10, we could deduce the invalidity of e . To show invalidity of e_0 , we proceed cases on the possible base formula of the LHS.

1. $e_1: \bar{\kappa} \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa'$ is stuck. By Proposition 4, e_1 is invalid. As $\bar{\kappa} \wedge \pi$ is an approximation of $\kappa \wedge \pi$, e_0 is invalid.
2. $e_2: \bar{\kappa} \wedge \pi \vdash \kappa'$ is derivable. And $\kappa' \equiv op(E) * \kappa''$. We proceed cases on $op(E)$.
 - $op(E) \equiv Q(x, F_3, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg_3)$. As the LHS is in NF, e_2 could be reduced by `RInd`. This implies that $x \mapsto c(F, \bar{d}, tg, u)[\bar{v}/\bar{d}] \wedge \pi_0[tg/scd] \in \bar{\kappa}$ and $x \neq F_3 \in \pi$. This implies that there are two possible sub-cases.
 - (a) Sub-case 1: $x \mapsto c(F, \bar{d}, tg, u)[\bar{v}/\bar{d}] \in \kappa$. As $x \neq F_3 \in \pi$, e_0 could be applied with `RInd`. It is impossible as it contradicts with the assumption that e_0 is stuck.
 - (b) Sub-case 2: $P(x, F, \bar{B}, u, sc, tg) \in \kappa$. As $x \neq F_3 \in \pi$, e_0 could be applied with `LInd`. As $x \neq F_3 \in \pi$, e_0 could be applied with `LInd`.
 - $op(E) \equiv x \mapsto c(next : F, \bar{v})$. Based on $x \mapsto c(next : F, \bar{v}) \in \bar{\kappa}$, there are two cases.

- (a) $x \mapsto c(\text{next} : F, \bar{v}) \in \kappa$. This contradicts with the assumption that $x \mapsto c(\text{next} : F, \bar{v})$ could not be matched with any predicate in κ . This case is impossible.
- (b) $P(x, E, ..) \in \kappa$. Any model satisfying the LHS when replacing $P(x, E, ..)$ by three-time unfolding (with two points-to predicates e.g., $x \mapsto c(\text{next} : F_1, ..) * F_1 \mapsto c(\text{next} : F, ..)$) is a counter-model.

□.

Proposition 5 (Incompleteness Preservation). *Given an input entailment $e_0: \Delta \vdash \Delta'$, and there is an leaf node $e_i: \Delta_l \vdash_{\kappa_m} \Delta'_l$ in its incomplete proof tree where*

- *the leaf node e_i is in NF; and*
- *none of application of rule FR from the root e_0 to the leaf node e_i ; and*
- *$\Delta_l \vdash \Delta'_l$ is not derivable.*

then e_0 is invalid.

Proof. By Lemma 13, e_i is invalid. By Lemma 6, e_0 is invalid.

□.